

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New 6-(Substituted-phenylazo)coumarin-3-carboxy-unsubstituted-anilides

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Compounds bearing azo groups¹ and azocoumarins² exhibit various biological activities¹. Though vast amount of work has been done on coumarins, little attention has been paid to the synthesis of coumarins using azosalicylaldehydes and malonanilic acids.

5-Substituted-phenylazosalicylaldehydes (1) have been prepared by diazotisation of aromatic amines and condensing them with salicylaldehyde (Scheme 1). 1 on reaction with malonanilic acids in the presence of condensing agents furnished the coumarins (2). Maximum yields (12–59%) of coumarins have been observed when piperidine was used as the condensing agent.

Biological activities : Compounds 1a, 1b, 2f and 2r were evaluated for antifungal activity by agar-plate food poisoning technique in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations and were found to be feebly active against *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizopus arrizus* and *Aspergillus niger* at the concentration indicated. Compounds 1a, 1b, 2c, 2h and 2u were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate technique and the per cent control was found in the range 15–30%. Compounds 2u, 2w, 2x, 2A and 2D were evaluated for *in vitro* anti-HIV activity⁵ which involves susceptible human

Scheme 1

host cells and the percent control on the infected plate was found in the range 5.21–8.26%.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	Colour	M.p./M.m.p. °C
2a	2-OC ₂ H ₅	H	Brown	190
b	2-OC ₂ H ₅	2-CH ₃	Black	170
c	2-OC ₂ H ₅	3-CH ₃	Light brown	195
d	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-CH ₃	Brown	155
e	2-OC ₂ H ₅	2-Cl	Brown	205
f	2-OC ₂ H ₅	3-Cl	Black	190
g	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-Cl	Light brown	190
h	2-OC ₂ H ₅	2-OCH ₃	Dark orange	230
i	2-OC ₂ H ₅	3-OCH ₃	Brown	140
j	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	Light brown	175
k	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	Dark brown	205
l	4-OC ₂ H ₅	2-CH ₃	Light brown	185
m	4-OC ₂ H ₅	3-CH ₃	Light brown	195
n	4-OC ₂ H ₅	4-CH ₃	Brown	140
o	4-OC ₂ H ₅	2-Cl	Dark brown	175
p	4-OC ₂ H ₅	3-Cl	Brown	120
q	4-OC ₂ H ₅	4-Cl	Light brown	180
r	4-OC ₂ H ₅	2-OCH ₃	Brown	195
s	4-OC ₂ H ₅	3-OCH ₃	Brown	200
t	4-OC ₂ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	Light brown	148
u	4-Br	H	Dark brown	244
v	4-Br	2-CH ₃	Brown	204
w	4-Br	3-CH ₃	Brown	182
x	4-Br	4-CH ₃	Brown	246
y	4-Br	2-Cl	Light brown	238
z	4-Br	3-Cl	Light brown	206
2A	4-Br	4-Cl	Brown	210
B	4-Br	2-OCH ₃	Brown	262
C	4-Br	3-OCH ₃	Brown	202
D	4-Br	4-OCH ₃	Brown	226

*All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. 5-Substituted-phenyl-azosalicylaldehydes³ and malonanilic acids⁴ were prepared by the reported methods.

5-(*o*-Ethoxyphenyl)azosalicylaldehyde (1a). *General procedure*: *o*-Phenatidine (4.5 ml) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (25 ml; 6*M*) and diazotised using sodium nitrite (4 g). A cold solution of salicylaldehyde (5 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (40 ml, 2 *N*) was added slowly with continuous stirring to the diazotised solution. The resulting dark orange solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol/acetic acid mixture (1 : 1): 1a (R=4-OEt) (60%), m.p. 105° (Found : N, 11.2. C₁₅H₁₄O₃N₂ requires : N, 10.37%); 1b (R=4-OEt) (65%), m.p. 90°; 1c (R=4-Br) (55%), m.p. 190°.

6-(*o*-Ethoxyphenylazo)coumarin-3-carboxyanilide (2a). *General procedure*: A mixture of malonanilic acid (0.9 g, 0.005 mol) and 1a (1.35 g, 0.005 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 120° when the mixture first melted and then set to a dark brown mass. The contents were cooled and digested with sodium bicarbonate solution and washed with water. The remaining residue was boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and filtered. The residue was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield dark brown crystals. Other compounds were similarly prepared (Table 1).

Ir spectra (KBr) of the coumarins (2) showed bands at 1 685–1 720 (C=O), 1 555–1 610 (azo) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (coumarin ring).

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